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journal homepage: <https://supportresult.uz/index.php/stdf>**INNOVATION AT THE CURRENT STAGE OF DEVELOPMENT OF THE ECONOMY IMPORTANCE OF ACTIVITIES****Sattorkulov Obidkul Turdikulovich**

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ИННОВАЦИИ НА СОВРЕМЕННОМ ЭТАПЕ РАЗВИТИЯ ЭКОНОМИКИ ВАЖНОСТЬ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ**Сатторов Обидкул Турдикулович**

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IQTISODIYOT RIVOJLANISHINING HOZIRGI BOSQICHIDAGI INNOVATSIYALAR FAOLIYATNING AHAMIYATI**Sattorov Obidqul Turdiqulovich**

Guliston davlat universiteti iqtisodiyot kafedrası dotsenti

abstract

This article presents the main ways in which innovation can have a positive impact on economic growth, welfare of the population, economic structure, social image of society and various sectors of the economy, innovation opportunities, their application and development prospects.

аннотация

В данной статье представлены основные способы, с помощью которых инновации могут оказать положительное влияние на экономический рост, благосостояние населения, экономическую структуру, социальный имидж общества и различных секторов экономики, возможности инноваций, их применение и перспективы развития.

annotatsiya

Ushbu maqolada innovatsiyalar iqtisodiy o'sishga, aholi farovonligiga, iqtisodiy tuzilishga, jamiyat va iqtisodiyotning turli tarmoqlarining ijtimoiy imidjiga, innovatsion imkoniyatlarga, ularni qo'llash va rivojlanish istiqbollariga ijobiy ta'sir ko'rsatishning asosiy usullari keltirilgan.

Keywords:

Innovation, novation, science, new development, innovation, innovation infrastructure, innovation activity, innovation process

Ключевые слова:

Инновация, новшество, наука, новая разработка, нововведение, инновационная инфраструктура, инновационная деятельность, инновационный процесс.

Kalit so'zlar:

Innovatsiya, yangilik, fan, yangi rivojlanish, innovatsiya, innovatsion infratuzilma, innovatsion faoliyat, innovatsion jarayon.

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Introduction

We stand on the position of the need to choose and implement an innovative development strategy, concentrate the efforts of the people, the state, and business on the development of fundamentally new, competitive technologies and products, innovative renewal of a critically outdated production apparatus, transition to an innovative path of development of the country, increasing the role and responsibility of the state for the choice and implementation of the strategy, for the development and dissemination of new generations engineering and technology, for the effectiveness of integration processes, for promoting the increase of innovative activity of entrepreneurs, scientists, designers, engineers – the young generation who will have to make fateful decisions and implement them in the coming decades. Only on this basis can high rates of economic growth and social development be ensured.

Research methodology

The foundations of the theory of innovative development were laid by N.Kondratiev, J. Schumpeter, P.Sorokin, S.Kuznetsov, G. Mensch, developed in the works of modern foreign and domestic researchers Kuzyk B.N., Yakovets Yu.B., Toshpulatov T., Rasulev A.F., Trostyansky D.V., etc. For example, our domestic researcher problems of innovative development of the economy D.N.Akabirova notes that “..the importance of science for the economy and society is determined not only by specific achievements. Scientific knowledge has no borders, and in the modern world many fruits of science can be used without having a powerful national science. However, there is a type of knowledge that cannot be obtained either in foreign literature or from a foreign expert. This knowledge is connected with the functions of science as a system-forming factor of the country's development.” [4]. In reality, sustainable economic and scientific-innovative development is not it may occur spontaneously. It requires the existence and successful functioning of a growth mechanism adequate to the situation, providing for the creation of the necessary economic, financial and organizational and legal conditions. Therefore, Russian researchers in the field of innovation A.K.Kazantsev and L.I. Mindeli, studying the importance of innovation for the economy as a whole, state that “..intensive factors are becoming crucial for economic dynamics. In turn, the growth of personnel qualifications and labor productivity, the return on materials and equipment is determined by the achievements of science and technology, best practices and the degree of their use in the economy, i.e. the spread of innovations. Contribution of scientific and technological progress to the increase in the gross domestic product of the most developed countries is, according to various estimates, from 75 to 90%.” [6].

In the domestic and foreign economic literature, there are various interpretations of such categories as "innovation", "innovation" and "innovation". In some cases, these concepts are used as synonyms, but there are certain differences between them.

The main topic of the research is the scientific study of patterns, trends and opportunities for the development of innovation in the economy of Uzbekistan today, in particular, the positive impact of innovation on various sectors of the economy. The development and prospects of our country, the success of large-scale reforms carried out in the republic directly depend on the introduction of innovations into our national economy. In the research work, such methods as observation, generalization, grouping, comparison, induction, deduction were used.

Results

Uzbekistan is in the process of transition to a qualitatively new stage of development based on innovation and science, within which the intangible sphere is turning into the most important factor of economic competitiveness. As noted by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh .Mirziyoyev in his message to the Oliy Majlis "... science and innovation create the basis for the development of the country" [1].

To date, the development of innovation is one of the main factors in the development of entrepreneurship and achieving success in the market. In the conditions of crisis and recession of the economic situation in the country, investing in innovations and their return is the direction that will help keep enterprises afloat. At the same time, it is worth considering that everything is not so simple and unambiguous. The effect of investing in innovations and their implementation in production processes depends on the institutional environment created in the country that regulates and promotes the development of the innovation sphere. One of the important stages in this direction was the creation of the Ministry of Innovative Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan, which implements a unified state policy in the field of innovation and scientific and technical development the republic, the formation of a Fund to support innovative development and innovative ideas under it. At the same time, a number of problems remain that hinder the establishment of effective mechanisms of interaction, strengthening the link between scientific research and production industries, which is primarily due to such factors as:

- firstly, low and unsatisfactory indicators of commercialization of the results of scientific works of higher educational institutions and research of research organizations;

- secondly, the lack of mechanisms to stimulate innovation processes, the implementation of comprehensive programs of innovative development and innovation activity at the regional and sectoral levels, support for innovative and active business entities;
- thirdly, insufficient involvement of representatives of the private sector in innovative activities, including due to their low interest;
- fourth, the lack of effective measures to improve the efficiency of the distribution and rational use of grants within the framework of state scientific and technical programs;
- fifth, the unsatisfactory level of international cooperation and attracting foreign investment in the field of scientific research and innovation.

Innovation is a new development introduced into civil circulation or used for its own needs, the application of which in practice ensures the achievement of a significant socio-economic effect [2]. Innovations show their exceptional usefulness with the same success as at the organizational level and at the economic level. There are several provisions of the impact of innovation on the state:

Under the influence of innovation, the entire structure of the economy is changing. After all, due to the increase in the efficiency of the use of resources, some of them are released and redistributed to other areas of activity. For example, the share of people employed in agriculture is decreasing, while in the service sector it is increasing. In addition, innovations are the direct cause of the emergence of new industries, industries and the gradual death of existing ones.

Innovations also change the economic organization of society. New public institutions and economic organizations are emerging and the content of the interrelations between them is being transformed. There are shifts in the ownership structure. Control technologies are being improved: vertical impacts are increasingly supplemented and replaced by horizontal ones. The content of state regulation of the economy is also undergoing changes. Based on world experience, there are 3 main approaches to the formation of state bodies responsible for the development of innovative processes:

1. Targeted regulation – there is a specific ministry or agency in the country whose sphere of activity includes directly only the regulation of innovation processes.

2. Related regulation – the regulation of innovation processes in the country is handled by a ministry or agency in which the regulation of innovation processes is only one of the directions and occurs in cooperation with some other or other directions.

3. Multiple regulation – several ministries or departments are responsible for regulating innovation processes, one of which has a dominant role and forms a common policy. At the same time, these state bodies can relate to both the first approach and the second. [3]

Innovation processes are becoming increasingly important socially. The economic growth generated by innovations not only improves the standard of living of the population, but also contributes to solving employment problems by creating new high-paying jobs, improving the level of education and healthcare. As the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan noted, "...2020, without exaggeration, has become a turning point in the field of social protection. First of all, for the first time recognizing the poverty of a certain category of the population, we have started a lot of work to reduce it. A fundamentally new system of targeted work with low-income families, women and youth has been introduced in all districts and cities, in every mahalla. In a short period, 527 thousand people were employed through this system" [1]. In addition, in the current historical period, the process of spreading innovations is one of the elements linking various social and economic actors into a single whole, ensuring the unity of the nation, in many cases mitigating social contradictions and conflicts.

The intensity of innovation processes in the modern world has significantly exacerbated environmental problems. The anthropogenic load on the environment in a number of directions is approaching a critical line, beyond which a violation of the normal circulation of substances in nature is inevitable. On the other hand, it is only through innovation that it is possible to harmonize the relationship between man and nature. After all, it is scientific and technical achievements that make it possible to reduce the use of irreplaceable resources and harmful emissions by rationalizing the structure of production and consumption, as well as the spread of recycling technologies. "We have set ourselves a great goal – the formation of the foundation of a new Renaissance in our country and for this purpose we must create an environment and conditions for the education of new Khorezmi, Beruni, Ibn Sino, Ulugbeks, Navoi and Baburs. The most important factors in this historical process, an integral part of our national idea are the development of education and upbringing, science and innovation, the establishment of a healthy lifestyle" [1].

By and large, innovations affect the economy as well as the organization only on a macroeconomic scale. The four main benefits of innovation for enterprises can also be transferred to the macroeconomic sphere:

-competitiveness increases (in this case, among the economies of different states). The competitiveness of a state is defined as "a measure of a country's ability, under conditions of a free and fair market, to produce goods and services that meet the

requirements of world markets while maintaining or increasing the real incomes of its citizens." [4]

-the quality of "products" is improving (it is replaced by the population at the economic level), i.e. the quality of life is growing

-production costs are saved (the economy requires less investment, becomes more self-governing)

-ensuring stable economic growth of the state.

The latter is the most important value, from which, by and large, the three previous ones follow. The importance of innovation for economic growth can be confirmed

numerous studies. For example, one of them took into account technological progress, not embodied in production factors (labor and capital), but the impact of the development of innovations by production, which provided additional profit. It turned out that innovations provide a huge additional profit, which other parallel developing countries cannot get without innovation, and which can be considered a generator of scientific institutions. According to estimates, the contribution of innovations to the development of the economy of our days is 60-70% (therefore, we can call the modern economy science-intensive). Economic growth is the dynamics of physical volumes of production and consumption of goods and services. Qualitative economic growth should be understood as the difference in development between one state and all others. It is provided through innovations, which are notable for the fact that they give the user additional economic profit. This additional profit serves as a difference in development between states, because any economic development rests on financial resources. It must be said that the functional role of innovation relations in the economic system also largely depends on what types of innovations are introduced into the economy. The decisive role in the development

of the economic system belongs to basic innovations, the conditions for mass development (innovation explosion) of which are created during the economic crisis at the depression phase (technical and technological stagnation). During this period, bundles (clusters) of basic innovations are formed, allowing to get out of this stagnation and ensure economic growth.

Economic growth will be ensured primarily by creating competitive production chains and increasing investments for these purposes. According to research by Harvard University, our country has all the opportunities and relative advantages in the production of industrial goods of more than 50 names. In particular, there are all conditions for the petrochemical, metallurgical, machine-building, electrical engineering, pharmaceutical, construction, textile, leather and footwear, food

industries, as well as areas related to the "green economy", to become the "drivers" of the national economy. [1]

Thus, innovations in the system of functioning of the economy act, by and large, as a material basis for improving production efficiency. They play a primary role in increasing the volume of output. For example, according to the calculations of foreign experts, the increase in national income due to innovations is estimated at 80-90%. Innovative activity, thus, gives an impetus to self-movement, is the primary impulse of imbalance and giving the economic mechanism of an active role and increases its synergetic effect. Therefore, in our republic, special importance is attached to the development of innovative activities and improvement of the management system of the sphere of science, in particular, the decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On approval of the Concept of Science development until 2030" dated October 29, 2020 is a confirmation of this. This concept provides for the following:

- improvement of the management system of the sphere of science;
- improvement of the system of financing science and scientific activities, as well as diversification of funding sources;
- training of highly qualified scientific and engineering personnel and their orientation to scientific activity;
- creation of a modern infrastructure for the development of science;
- formation of a modern information environment that contributes to the development of science. [5].

The value of innovation can also be represented in the form of socio-economic functions performed by this phenomenon:

1).The first function is that almost all inventions are aimed at reducing the cost of energy, living labor, create opportunities to involve new production forces in production, increase the efficiency of labor and production.

2).The second function of innovation is to improve the quality of manufactured products, which leads to an increase in the level of production and consumption, contributes to improving the quality of life.

3).The third function of innovation is that by improving quality, reducing costs and improving consumption, they contribute to maintaining the proportions between supply and demand, between production and consumption.

4). And, finally, the fourth function - in the course of development, when using innovations, a person develops - his intellectual abilities are realized, conditions for further creative growth are created.

In connection with all of the above, today the most important goal in the field of improving innovation activity is the formation of a unified state policy aimed at

determining the prospects and mechanisms that ensure the activation of innovation processes as a source of economic growth in the medium and long term.

Conclusion

1. The need for state regulation of innovation processes is caused primarily by their increasing importance for the economy and society as a whole. In the modern era, the opportunities for the growth of output of products and services due to increased employment of the able-bodied population and the involvement of new natural resources in economic turnover are becoming increasingly limited. Intensive factors are becoming crucial for economic dynamics. In turn, the growth of personnel qualifications and labor productivity, the return on materials and equipment is determined by the achievements of science and technology, best practices and the degree of their use in the economy, i.e. the spread of innovations.

2. The contribution of scientific and technological progress to the growth of the gross domestic product of the most developed countries is, according to various estimates, from 75 to 90%. Thus, the first aspect of the national significance of innovations is their decisive influence on macroeconomic indicators. The structure of the economy is also changing under the influence of innovative processes. Due to the increase in the efficiency of the use of resources, some of them are released and redistributed to other areas of activity.

3. Innovations are the direct cause of the emergence of some industries and industries, the gradual extinction and disappearance of others. The impact on the structure of social production is the second aspect of the national significance of innovation processes. Innovations also change the economic organization of society. New elements appear in the spectrum of the main economic structures (for example, venture firms), the content of the relationships between them is transformed.

4. A significant impact on institutional economic mechanisms is the third aspect of the national importance of innovation. The impact of innovative processes is experienced not only by production, but also by almost all aspects of public life. The structure of consumption of both tangible and intangible goods is being improved. Political culture is developing. Legal, ethical, and aesthetic norms are changing dynamically.

5. The fourth aspect of the national significance of innovation processes is the increasing identity of the nation's ability to progress and its potential in production and implementation of innovations. Innovative processes are becoming increasingly social. Along with the fact that the already noted economic growth generated by innovations makes it possible to improve the standard of living of the population, innovations often contribute to solving employment problems by creating new high-paying jobs.

6. In the current historical period, the process of spreading innovations is one of the elements connecting various social and economic entities into a single whole, ensures the unity of the nation, in many cases mitigates social contradictions and conflicts. And so, the impact of innovation processes on social stability is the fifth aspect of the overall national importance of innovation.

7. The intensity of innovation processes in the modern world has significantly exacerbated environmental problems. The anthropogenic load on the environment in a number of directions is approaching a critical line, which is inevitably followed by a violation of the normal circulation of substances in nature. However, it is only on the innovative path that the harmonization of relations between man and nature is possible.

8. Scientific and technical achievements allow to reduce the use of irreplaceable resources and harmful emissions by rationalizing the structure of production and consumption, as well as the spread of recycling technologies. These problems are especially relevant in the light of the adoption by the world community of the concept of sustainable development in the XXI century, which provides for a stable ecological balance.

9. The impact of innovations on the environment is the sixth aspect of the national significance of innovation processes. The past century has been marked by the rapid internationalization of economic life. International in nature, often with innovative processes also acquire advanced integration depth. The cooperation of various countries in the innovation sphere takes place in a wide range of forms —pooling resources in order to obtain new scientific and technical results, international technology transfer in both an embodied and non-embodied form, the creation of a global scientific and innovation infrastructure, the implementation of innovations that are global in nature, etc.

10. When on the modern scale of scientific and technological progress, many innovative projects cannot be implemented by one, even by the most developed country. The intensification of international scientific and technical cooperation is the seventh aspect of the national importance of innovation processes. However, full integration into global innovation processes is impossible without the country having an adequate scientific and technological base, as well as mechanisms to ensure the perception of innovations from abroad. The level and effectiveness of the country's inclusion in the international division of labor are characterized by its position in the world markets of goods and services, as well as the presence of qualified specialists. This position is increasingly determined by the exclusive possession of natural

resources or other temporary advantages of an extensive nature, and to a greater extent by innovations that ensure the competitiveness of products.

11. The eighth aspect of the national importance of innovation is the dependence of the global competitiveness of the national economy on the level of development of innovation processes.

12. The relationship between the levels of scientific and innovative potential and national security is the ninth aspect of the national importance of innovation. The ability to innovate has now become one of the most important determinants of State security. This position has both external and internal components. As for the international side, we are talking here about ensuring scientific and technological security, i.e. the country has a sufficiently powerful scientific and innovative potential that allows it to resist any dictate from the outside associated with restricting access to advanced technologies, breaking the main established technological chains. The development of scientific and innovative potential for strengthening the country's defense capability is especially important. At the same time, the internationalization of scientific, technical and innovative processes reduces the threat of conflicts due to the increasing technological interdependence of countries. The internal side of the issue is connected with the spread of innovations that allow preventing disasters, natural disasters, terrorist acts, and other illegal actions, as well as minimizing their negative consequences.

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